

Development of Digital Learning and Literacy with the Socialization of Digital Library and E-Learning in Cuwelo 1 Elementary School

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ABSTRACT

SD Cuwelo 1 is located in Candirejo sub-district, Soka hamlet, RT 03 RW 13. Soka hamlet is on Jalan Baron, east of Cuwelo Kidul hamlet and west of Gebang hamlet. The implementation of education at the school runs effectively every Monday to Saturday with several additional extracurricular activities from the school. SD Cuwelo 1 school received 30 notebooks from the local government to improve learning, especially in the digital and information technology fields. Because of this potential, the real work lecture program is related to increasing teacher and student understanding of the importance of developing educational structures and digitization of education by socializing it to schools. The socialization was carried out 1 time with a duration of 90 minutes. The first 30 minutes explained in general about digitalization, educational transformation, ebooks in general, and the digital library of the Muhammadiyah University of Yogyakarta. Then the second 30 minutes was the application of learning management system, digital library of Yogyakarta Muhammadiyah University and e-books in general developed by the government and private sector. and the last 30 minutes of direct application by students and questions and answers related to socialization material on that day. After the socialization takes place, it is hoped that students and students will still be connected with real work college students regarding the continuation of this socialization.

KEYWORDS

digitalization;
educational transformation;
ebooks in general;
digital library

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1. Introduction

A digital library is a digital library that contains books, pictures, audio and video in digital form. The purpose of a digital library is to make it easier for users to access books, practically brought to all places, can be used anywhere and anytime, cheaper prices for books, and their distribution. easier. with this convenience and changes to the curriculum and modern learning structure, the improvement of learning at Cuwelo Elementary School is very relevant to the potential and development of the times. from the programs that we have carried out, previous research on learning media, elementary age education, digitalization of , and the transformation of learning needs to be referred to. Several previous researchers have examined this issue, for example: collaborative digital libraries for children were researched. Linking scientific digital libraries in Digital Humanities: a case study of IMAGO researched by Bartalesi [1]. User Navigation in Large-Scale Distributed Digital Libraries: The Case of American Digital Public Libraries researched by Matusiak [2]. The silver lining of the COVID-19 crisis for digital libraries in terms of remote access was researched by Pokorná [3]. Document Image Compression with Applications for Digital Preservation in Digital Libraries researched by ZHANG [4]. A study of non-users of digital libraries: the case of the Capes digital library in Brazil investigated by Fernandes [5]. Capisco: low-cost concept-based access to digital libraries researched by Hinze [6].

Towards efficient navigation in digital libraries: Leveraging popularity, semantics and community to recommend scientific research articles by Yadav [7]. Digital Library musicology was researched by Lewis [8]. Automatic Fake News Detection in the Digital Library Age was researched by Mertoğlu [9]. Visual Search in Digital Libraries and Use of External Terms was researched by Hajra [10]. A new subject-based search and search result visualization approach for scientific digital libraries was researched by Bakhshayesh [11]. Distribution of dated and modified elements by digital library types: Analyzing the metadata set of a large-scale Polish distributed system researched by Osinska [12].

Research on students' willingness to use university digital libraries: affinity theory as an additional construct of the information system success model studied by Xu [13]. Agent-oriented and ontology-based digital libraries: the IndianaMAS experience researched by Briola [14]. Understanding extended information search was researched by Zha [15]. The Importance of Digital Libraries and Their Requirements - Case Study: National Research Center, Initiative to Build Sudanese Digital Libraries researched by Ahmed Juma [16]. Digital Library Development with Software Product Line Engineering was researched by Pedreira [17]. Emerging scenarios of data infrastructure and digital library new concepts in intelligent infrastructure for empowered human communities: A qualitative research conducted by Shen [18].

Maintaining multilingualism: a case study of two multilingual digital libraries researched by Wu [19]. Semantic Search-by-Examples for Corpus Expansion of Scientific Topics in Digital Libraries was researched by Al-Natsheh [20]. refine the model to identify antecedents and provide user satisfaction with digital libraries researched by Soltani-Nejad [21]. Evaluation of the accessibility of archival cartographic documents in digital libraries researched by Kuzma [22]. Thinking of digital libraries for preservation as digital cultural heritage: with the R to R4 aspect of the FAIR principle researched by Barbuti [23]. Digital libraries: leverage Twitter to build online communities researched by Xie [24].

Derrida and digital libraries: exploring impossibility of virtual hospitality researched by Mestre [25]. Ontology scientific documents for semantic representation of digital libraries was researched by Elizarov [26]. The strategy for implementing the adoption of digital library research support services in academic libraries in Indonesia was researched by Maryati [27]. Semantic web and ontology-based applications for digital libraries were researched by Khan [28]. A deep structured neural network technique to improve the classification of homonyms and synonyms of authors in digital libraries was researched by Firdaus [29]. Examining the differences and convenience between placement student and undergraduate user satisfaction with digital libraries was investigated by Xu [30]. The problem of media stagnation and the existing educational structure must be resolved as best as possible and become a KKN 072 work program. This article explains innovations and solutions to SD Cuwelo 1. The innovations and solutions in question are socializing learning media, digitizing education, and learning transformation, where these points are explained with digital libraries, learning management systems, and several Android applications.

2. Method

Information about education in the Soka hamlet, especially in SD Cuwelo 1, is something that must be thought about and implemented, one of which is by socializing the digital library. The KKN 072 team as students who have knowledge and application in the field of education have contributed to educational innovation in the Soka hamlet. The KKN 072 team offers ideas for implementing student learning, especially educational transformation in the digital field which can be applied in schools with digital libraries and e-learning. Based on Figure 1, it can be seen that there are 4 stages of activity in carrying out this program. The first step in this program is observing general educational problems in the Soka hamlet. The second is discussions with teachers regarding learning and learning facilities at school. The third step is digital socialization. library and E-learning in schools. step four, monitoring learning applications that have been socialized

Fig. 1. The method for implementing UMY KKN activities.

3. Results and Discussion

Observations

During the first and second KKN observations, TI 072 held discussions with local residents in Soka hamlet, Candirejo village, Gunungkidul sub-district, Yogyakarta. These activities were carried out to find out the problems and potential of the hamlet, including general education problems. As shown in Figures 2 and 3, after making observations with discussions with various parties, information was found that SD Cuwelo 1 received a grant of 30 notebooks from the local government. On the other hand, the main theme given by the campus is the digital library and socializing it actively and well with the school's program, the socialization is related to educational transformation, which includes campus programs that have great potential

Fig. 2. First observation with the village head and community leaders

Fig. 3. Observation 2 with the hamlet

Discussion

The KKN 072 team visited the school directly. The visit was carried out with the aim of friendly relations, socialization permits and discussion regarding the program to be carried out. the school really

welcomed the program that the 072 team wanted to do. the necessary facilities such as projectors and notebooks are available and all that remains is to prepare for the socialization day. From this discussion, the teachers gave some direction regarding socialization for the smooth running of the program

Socialization

After obtaining permission and directions from the teacher, the KKN 072 team conducted digital library outreach to Cuwelo 1 Elementary School on August 20. As shown in Figure 4, the KKN 072 team explains the materials that have been prepared and the tools needed. The explanation is done with a projector and is watched directly by students who can later apply it directly.

Fig. 4. Digital library socialization at SD Cuwelo 1

Monitoring

After the socialization was carried out, students and teachers continued to communicate with the KKN 072 team to ensure understanding of the use of the application and certainty of running the program. Teachers and students can ask technical and non-technical matters related to digital libraries and e-learning.

4. Conclusion

SD Cuwelo 1 is an educational institution in Soka Hamlet. After the observation, the learning media at the school can still be improved by providing additional knowledge related to digital libraries and E-learning. With this program, it is hoped that students and teachers can adjust the independent curriculum that has been initiated by the ministry of education, where education does not only prioritize academics, but also cognitive psychology which can be obtained with various existing android applications as well as readings, audio, videos in the library digital. on the other hand the effectiveness of the time and place of learning, evaluation of parents which can be seen from the E-learning system is an adjustment and improvement of existing learning media.

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Author Contribution

the author's contribution in community service is to offer ideas for implementing student learning, especially the transformation of education in the digital field which can be applied in schools with digital libraries and e-learning.

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Conflict of Interest

The authors declare no conflict of interest.

References

- [1] V. Bartalesi, N. Pratelli, and E. Lenzi, "Linking different scientific digital libraries in Digital Humanities: the IMAGO case study," *Int. J. Digit. Libr.*, vol. 23, no. 4, pp. 303–317, Dec. 2022.
- [2] K. K. Matusiak, "User Navigation in Large-Scale Distributed Digital Libraries: The Case of the Digital Public Library of America," *J. Web Librariansh.*, vol. 11, no. 3–4, pp. 157–171, Oct. 2017.
- [3] L. Pokorná, M. Inđrák, M. Grman, F. Stepanovsky, and M. Smetánková, "Silver lining of the COVID-19 crisis for digital libraries in terms of remote access," *Digit. Libr. Perspect.*, vol. 36, no. 4, pp. 389–401, Aug. 2020.
- [4] Y. ZHANG, Y. ZHAO, and G. LI, "Document Image Compression with Application to Digital Preservation in Digital Libraries," in *2018 IEEE International Conference on Signal Processing, Communications and Computing (ICSPCC)*, 2018, pp. 1–4.
- [5] W. R. Fernandes and B. V. Cendón, "A study of non-users of digital libraries: the case of the Capes digital library in Brazil," *Electron. Libr.*, vol. 39, no. 5, pp. 661–677, Nov. 2021.
- [6] A. Hinze et al., "Capisco: low-cost concept-based access to digital libraries," *Int. J. Digit. Libr.*, vol. 20, no. 4, pp. 307–334, Dec. 2019.
- [7] P. Yadav and N. Pervin, "Towards efficient navigation in digital libraries: Leveraging popularity, semantics and communities to recommend scholarly articles," *J. Informetr.*, vol. 16, no. 4, p. 101336, Nov. 2022.
- [8] D. Lewis, Y. Fan, G. Henshaw, and K. Page, "Musicology of Digital Libraries," in *Proceedings of the 4th International Workshop on Digital Libraries for Musicology*, 2017, pp. 59–62.
- [9] U. Mertoğlu and B. Genç, "Automated Fake News Detection in the Age of Digital Libraries," *Inf. Technol. Libr.*, vol. 39, no. 4, Dec. 2020.
- [10] A. Hajra and K. Tochtermann, "Visual Search in Digital Libraries and the Usage of External Terms," in *2018 22nd International Conference Information Visualisation (IV)*, 2018, pp. 396–400.
- [11] S. M. Bakhshayesh, A. Ahmadi, and A. Mohebi, "A new subject-based retrieval and search result visualization approach for scientific digital libraries," *Electron. Libr.*, vol. 39, no. 4, pp. 572–595, Nov. 2021.

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- [12] V. Osinska, K. K. Matusiak, M. Kowalska, B. Bednarek-Michalska, and P. Malak, "Distribution of date elements and its relationship to the types of digital libraries: Analysing aggregated metadata of a Polish large-scale distributed system," *J. Librariansh. Inf. Sci.*, vol. 51, no. 3, pp. 710–720, Sep. 2019.
- [13] F. Xu and J. T. Du, "Research on the drivers of undergraduates' intention to use university digital libraries: affinity theory as an additional construct of information system success model," *Libr. Hi Tech*, vol. 40, no. 6, pp. 1627–1641, Dec. 2022.
- [14] D. Briola, V. Deufemia, V. Mascardi, and L. Paolino, "Agent-oriented and ontology-driven digital libraries: the IndianaMAS experience," *Softw. Pract. Exp.*, vol. 47, no. 11, pp. 1773–1799, Nov. 2017.
- [15] X. Zha, C. Huang, Y. Yan, G. Yan, X. Wang, and K. Zhang, "Understanding extended information seeking," *Aslib J. Inf. Manag.*, vol. 72, no. 5, pp. 705–724, Sep. 2020.
- [16] N. H. Ahmed Juma, "The Importance of Digital Libraries and Requirements - Case Study: The National Center for Research, Initiative to Establish the Sudanese Digital Library," in 2018 JCCO Joint International Conference on ICT in Education and Training, International Conference on Computing in Arabic, and International Conference on Geocomputing (JCCO: TICET-ICCA-GECO), 2018, pp. 1–5.
- [17] O. Pedreira, D. Ramos-Vidal, A. Cortiñas, M. Luaces, and A. Saavedra-Places, "Development of Digital Libraries with Software Product Line Engineering," *J. Web Eng.*, Nov. 2021.
- [18] Y. Shen, "Emerging scenarios of data infrastructure and novel concepts of digital libraries in intelligent infrastructure for human-centred communities: A qualitative research," *J. Inf. Sci.*, vol. 45, no. 5, pp. 691–704, Oct. 2019.
- [19] A. Wu and J. Chen, "Sustaining multilinguality: case studies of two multilingual digital libraries," *Electron. Libr.*, vol. 40, no. 6, pp. 625–645, Nov. 2022.
- [20] H. T. Al-Natsheh, L. Martinet, F. Muhlenbach, F. Rico, and D. A. Zighed, "Semantic Search-by-Examples for Scientific Topic Corpus Expansion in Digital Libraries," in 2017 IEEE International Conference on Data Mining Workshops (ICDMW), 2017, pp. 747–756.
- [21] N. Soltani-Nejad, F. Taheri-Azad, N. Zarei-Maram, and M. K. Saberi, "Developing a model to identify the antecedents and consequences of user satisfaction with digital libraries," *Aslib J. Inf. Manag.*, vol. 72, no. 6, pp. 979–997, Nov. 2020.
- [22] M. Kuzma and A. Moscicka, "Evaluation of the accessibility of archival cartographic documents in digital libraries," *Electron. Libr.*, vol. 36, no. 6, pp. 1062–1081, Nov. 2018.
- [23] N. Barbuti, "Thinking digital libraries for preservation as digital cultural heritage: by R to R4 facet of FAIR principles," *Int. J. Digit. Libr.*, vol. 22, no. 3, pp. 309–318, Sep. 2021.
- [24] I. Xie and J. A. Stevenson, "@Digital libraries: harnessing Twitter to build online communities," *Online Inf. Rev.*, vol. 43, no. 7, pp. 1263–1283, Nov. 2019.
- [25] J. Mestre, "Derrida and digital libraries: exploring the (im)possibility of virtual hospitality," *Inf. Res. an Int. Electron. J.*, vol. 27, Oct. 2022.
- [26] A. Elizarov, S. Khaydarov, and E. Lipachev, "Scientific documents ontologies for semantic representation of digital libraries," in 2017 Second Russia and Pacific Conference on Computer Technology and Applications (RPC), 2017, pp. 1–5.
- [27] I. Maryati, B. Purwandari, H. Budi Santoso, and I. Budi, "Implementation Strategies for Adopting Digital Library Research Support Services in Academic Libraries in Indonesia," in 2020 International Conference on Informatics, Multimedia, Cyber and Information System (ICIMCIS), 2020, pp. 188–194.
- [28] S. A. Khan and R. Bhatti, "Semantic Web and ontology-based applications for digital libraries," *Electron. Libr.*, vol. 36, no. 5, pp. 826–841, Nov. 2018.
- [29] F. Firdaus et al., "Neural network technique with deep structure for improving author homonym and synonym classification in digital libraries," *TELKOMNIKA (Telecommunication Comput. Electron. Control.*, vol. 19, no. 4, p. 1208, Aug. 2021.
- [30] F. Xu and J. T. Du, "Examining differences and similarities between graduate and undergraduate students' user satisfaction with digital libraries," *J. Acad. Librariansh.*, vol. 45, no. 6, p. 102072, Nov. 2019.
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